

Coordinating Properties of a New Pyrazole-derived (ONS)-Tridentate : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) with 1-Thiocarbamyl-5-Methyl Pyrazole-3-Carboxylic Acid and Heterocyclic Amines

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The coordination behaviour of a new pyrazole-derived ONS-tridentate, 1-thiocarbamyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid (abbreviated as ONSH₃) has been studied by complexation with copper(II). Mixed-ligand complexes of general composition Cu(ONS)B.nH₂O [B=py/(α-, β- and γ-)pico/bipy/o-phen; n=2,4,5] have been isolated and characterised by various physico-chemical techniques; the complexes have usual distorted octahedral configurations as revealed from magnetic and electronic spectral data. The species, [Cu(ONS)].2H₂O, is given a bridged dimeric structure occurring through thiocarbamyl group of the ligand. The i.r. data suggest a diprotic ONS-tridentate behaviour of the primary ligand molecule (in its 'thiol' form) in all the complex species.

THE biological implications of both heterocyclic carboxylic acid and its derivatives¹ as well as the thiosemicarbazones containing N-heterocycles² have prompted us to design a new pyrazole based ONS-tridentate, 1-thiocarbamyl-5-methylpyrazole-3-carboxylic acid (ONSH₃; Fig. 1) which might have potentiality in complexing metal ions of biological

reaction between sodium salt of ethyl acetopyruvate and thiosemicarbazide following a method³ similar to that adopted for the preparation of 5(3)-methyl pyrazole-3(5)-carboxylic acid. The pale yellow compound on recrystallisation from ethanol melts at 204-206° (with decomposition) and is fairly soluble in low molecular weight alcohols and acetone.

Fig. 1

importance. The present communication is intended to report the coordination tendencies of this potentially tridentate ligand molecule by complexation with Cu(II) often in presence of heterocyclic amines.

Experimental

A. Preparation of the Ligand :

1-Thiocarbamyl-5-methylpyrazole-3-carboxylic acid (ONSH₃) was prepared from the condensation

Anal. : C, 39.53 ; H, 3.98 ; N, 22.50%.

Calcd. for C₆H₇N₂O₂S : C, 38.91 ; H, 3.86 ;
N, 22.59%.

UV bands in nm : $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 212 (log ϵ ~ 3.92) ; 239
(log ϵ ~ 3.91) ; 289 (log ϵ ~ 3.99).

B. Preparation of the Complexes :

(i) [Cu(ONS)].2H₂O :

The complex corresponding to the composition [Cu(ONS)].2H₂O, was prepared by mixing copper(II) chloride dihydrate (0.01 mole) and the ligand (0.01 mole) in aqueous ethanol; immediate precipitation of the brown coloured compound occurred on stirring. It was filtered, washed with aqueous alcohol and then dried over anhydrous CaCl₂.

(ii) Cu(ONS).B.nH₂O where B=py/pico (α-, β- and γ-)/bipy/o-phen; n=2,4,5 :

These mixed-ligand complexes were prepared by a general method; the parent complex, Cu(ONS).2H₂O (0.002 mole) was dissolved in the corresponding base [in the case of solid base like bipy/o-phen, ethanolic solution of the same (0.002 mole)] with

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	%Cu	%N	%S
I. [Cu(ONS)].2H ₂ O	brown	22.40 (22.48)*	14.91 (14.86)	11.12 (11.31)
II. [Cu(ONS)py.2H ₂ O]	blue	17.61 (17.55)	15.47 (15.48)	8.62 (8.86)
III. [Cu(ONS) α -pico.2H ₂ O]	blue	17.04 (16.90)	14.95 (14.90)	8.88 (8.59)
IV. [Cu(ONS) β -pico.2H ₂ O].2H ₂ O	pale blue	15.50 (15.43)	13.51 (13.60)	7.91 (7.78)
V. [Cu(ONS) γ -pico.2H ₂ O]	pale blue	16.80 (16.90)	14.87 (14.90)	8.69 (8.59)
VI. [Cu(ONS)bipy.H ₂ O]	bluish green	15.07 (15.10)	16.76 (16.65)	7.40 (7.62)
VII. [Cu(ONS) <i>o</i> -phen.H ₂ O].4H ₂ O	apple green	12.33 (12.29)	13.52 (13.55)	6.00 (6.19)

ONSH_n = One molecule of 1-thiocarbamyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid.

* The respective calculated values are in parentheses.

TABLE 2—SOME IMPORTANT PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	μ_{eff} in B.M. (at °K)	Absorption maxima in cm ⁻¹ *	Molar conductance Λ_m , in ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹ taking 1 × 10 ⁻³ M methanol solution at 30°
I. [Cu(ONS)].2H ₂ O	1.55 (304)	23,800br; 14,300sh ^a 13,300br ^b	—
II. [Cu(ONS)py.2H ₂ O]	1.77 (304)	14,100(87.4)br ^c	9.67
III. [Cu(ONS) α -pico.2H ₂ O]	1.83 (301)	13,900(66.7)br ^c	12.48
IV. [Cu(ONS) β -pico.2H ₂ O].2H ₂ O	1.81 (302)	15,200(87.6)sh; 14,100(99.4)br ^c	10.08
V. [Cu(ONS) γ -pico.2H ₂ O]	1.87 (302)	13,900(81.0)br ^c	14.21
VI. [Cu(ONS)bipy.H ₂ O]	1.97 (302)	19,900(217.9)br ^d	4.05 ^e
VII. [Cu(ONS) <i>o</i> -phen.H ₂ O].4H ₂ O	1.82 (302)	14,100(240.1)br; 13,600(233.6)wsh ^d	8.12 ^e

* Molar extinction coefficients in parentheses.

a. mull spectrum; b. spectrum in DMF; c. spectrum in methanol; d. spectrum in nitromethane;

e. conductance measurements in nitromethane solution.

occasional stirring and the resulting mixture was kept over-night; the solution obtained after filtration was allowed to concentrate at room temperature for 24 hours; coloured microcrystalline compound separated; this was collected and dried in each case in the usual way.

The physico-chemical measurements were carried out as described earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data on which the compositions of the complexes are based, are shown in Table 1, while other pertinent physico-chemical data are placed in Table 2.

The complex species, Cu(ONS)B.nH₂O [B = py/pico (α -, β - and γ -)bipy/*o*-phen; n = 2, 4, 5] are insoluble in water, but fairly soluble in common organic solvents like methanol, acetone and nitromethane. Methanol or nitromethane solutions show molar conductivities of the order of 4-14 ohm⁻¹cm²

mole⁻¹ which indicate their non-electrolyte nature in the said solvent. The room temperature magnetic moment values (μ_{eff} = 1.77–1.97 B.M.) are consistent with distorted octahedral configurations of the complexes. Methanol or nitromethane solutions of the complexes furnish spectral curves showing in each case, a broad envelope covering the region 13,500-14,100 cm⁻¹ with maxima and shoulder, both often diffused, which may originate from the overlap functions of the three close-in-energy transitions: ²B₁ → ²A₁ (ν_1); ²B₁ → ²B₂ (ν_2) and ²B₁ → ²E (ν_3), producing distorted octahedral environment for the complexes⁵.

The brown compound, Cu(ONS).2H₂O offers some unique features in its magnetic and spectral behaviour. The compound which is insoluble in water and innocent organic solvents and is fairly soluble in coordinating solvents like pyridine, methyl pyridines, DMF etc., shows subnormal magnetic moment value of 1.55 B.M. at room temperature; although magnetic data over a temperature could not be recorded, yet the subnormal value

TABLE 3—I.R. SPECTRAL BANDS (in cm^{-1}) OF THE LIGANDS AND ITS COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

ONSH _a	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	Probable assignment
3480s 3390ssh 3340ssh 3270bs 2980wsh 2940wsh	9440- 9060bs 2960bsh	3450- 3000bs 2940wb	3460- 3000bs 2950wb	3450- 3000bs 2950wb	3460- 3000bs 2940wb	3480- 3000bs 2950wb	3460- 3000bs 2960wb	} $\nu_{\text{OH}} + \nu_{\text{NH}}$
	2180ms ; 2090ms 2090ms	2090w	2090w	2090w	2100w	2100vs	2090vs	
1725s	1660wsh , 1620vs	1650s	1630s	1635vs	1640vs	1600vs	1610vs	$\nu_{\text{asymCO}_2^-}$
1600s 1565sh 1470s	1600w 1570sh 1510w 1475wsh	1615ms 1600ms 1500ms	1605ms 1595sh 1500ms	1610ms 1580sh 1505ms	1600ms 1530ssh 1510s	1570ms 1510s	1580ms 1500s	} $\delta_{\text{NH}_2} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$
1430s 1380w 1360w 1310ms 1270s	1425ms 1350sh 1320s 1300s 1275sh	1400ms 1380w 1340w 1290s	1400ms 1360s 1300w	1410ms 1350ms 1280s	1360ms 1295ms	1370w 1290s	1340ms 1290w	
1120s	1120w , 1100s	1090sh , 1070ms	1100wsh	1085ms	1120w	1105w 1107w	1100w	} Amide-III $\nu_{\text{NH}_2} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}} + \nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$
1015ms 980ms	1035m 1015w	1040ms 1030ms 1010wsh	1060ms	1020ms	1040ms	1040s 1020ms	1030ms	
895s 785s	840w , 800m 780w 700ms —	835ms , 810s 760s 700s 1450s	795ms 700s 1445s	800s 740s 705s 1460s	810sh 800s 700s 1440s	780s 800s 725s 1480s 1450vs 735vs	840ms 770s 700ms 1485s 1440vs 730vs 890ms	} $\nu_{\text{NH}_2} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ Characteristic vibra- tions of the co-ligand Characteristic frequency of coordinated water molecule
	—	850ms	850ms	860ms	840ms	870ms	890ms	

s=strong , w=weak , b=broad , v=very , m=medium , sh=shoulder. I to VII-Compounds in serial order as in Tables 1 and 2.

is suggestive of the existence of dimers or polymers with possible Cu—Cu interaction. The mull spectrum of the compound exhibits a broad absorption band centred around $23,800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a shoulder at ca. $14,300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (the spin-allowed d-d transitions are presumably obscured by the intense charge transfer band⁶), while the DMF solution of the compound produces a single broad band at $\sim 13,300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2). The compound is thought to have a dimeric structure, where the dimerisation might be effective through the bridging nature of thiocarbamyl group of the ligand molecule (like the bridging SCN group⁷⁻⁹) as is supported from the appearance of two newly developed i.r. bands at 2180 cm^{-1} (ms) and 2090 cm^{-1} (ms) (see Table 3 of i.r. spectra) with antiferromagnetic interaction in the solid state and on dissolution in coordinating solvents the dimeric structure is broken and consequently a distorted octahedral species is formed.

The recognisable i.r. bands of the primary ligand (ONSH_a) and its copper(II) complexes with probable assignments¹⁰⁻¹⁶ are summarised in Table 3. The absence of any S—H band around 2500 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the free ligand excludes the possibility of the existence of its 'thiol' form [Fig.1b] at least in the solid state.

The spectra of the metal complexes are mostly complicated due to the presence of additional base molecules as co-ligands. However, on a closer scrutiny the following observations/conclusions seem relevant :

(i) The broad bands at 3μ region are indicative of extensive intra and/or intermolecular hydrogen bonding in the complex species.

(ii) The newly developed bands at 2100 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the metal complexes may be assignable to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ which arises due to the participation of thiocarbamyl residue in complex formation through the enolised 'thiol' form of the ligand.

(iii) The asymmetric $\nu_{\text{CO}_2^-}$ of the free ligand [at 1725 cm^{-1} (s)] has been found to shift towards lower frequency region ($\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in all the metal complexes indicating the participation of carboxylic acid group of the ligand molecule in complexation.

(iv) The bands around 1600 cm^{-1} (which are mainly ascribed to δ_{NH_2} of the thiocarbamyl group

of the free ligand) are found to experience subtle changes on complex formation.

(v) The participation of thiocarbonyl group in complexation is generally considered in the light of its following canonical forms :

The forms II and III are more accessible due to higher polarisability of sulphur atom¹⁷ and evidently then the metal attachment through sulphur leads to a decrease in the thiocarbonyl stretching force and an increase of C-N frequency¹⁸⁻²⁰. In the present case, the i.r. bands observed around 1500 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes correspond to 1470 cm⁻¹ band of the free ligand molecule, which is assigned to N-C-N (B₁) stretching vibration of the thiosemicarbazide derivative. The observed increase in frequency may be explained as resulting from enhanced double bond character of C-N bond on complex formation through the 'thiol' form. In addition the observed bands at 1430 cm⁻¹(s), 1310 cm⁻¹(ms), 1120 cm⁻¹(s) and 895 cm⁻¹(s) which are attributed to the combined vibrations of δNH_2 or δNH_2 coupled with $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ and/or $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$, suffer appreciable changes; the most notable change, however, occurs in the region of 785 cm⁻¹(s), which is ascribed to $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ of the ligand molecule. All these bands have either become weak and shifted to the lower frequency side or have disappeared on complex formation; the observation may be accounted for by considering appreciable decrease in the bond order of C=S bond on participation in bonding to the metal through sulphur atom.

(vi) The medium strong bands at 1015 cm⁻¹ and 980 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to $\nu\text{N}-\text{N}$ of the pyrazole ring system coupled with δNH_2 , are found to shift towards higher frequency side [~ 1040 cm⁻¹(s)] indicating the pyridine nitrogen atom of the pyrazole ring as a coordination site. This is in conformity with X-ray crystallographic results of several pyrazole metal complexes²¹⁻²³.

(vii) The presence of secondary co-ligands, e.g., pyridine and methyl pyridines, are inferred from their vibrations²⁴ in the region of 1600-1400 cm⁻¹ (Table 3). The characteristic vibrations of bipyridyl and o-phenanthroline have also been recognised²⁵ showing their presence in the respective adducts (Table 3). The broadness of the bands at 3 μ region and medium strong bands around 850-900 cm⁻¹ suggest the presence of coordinated water molecules²⁶ in all these mixed-ligand complexes. Thermal treatment, carried out in a manual TG balance at heating rate of 7°/min, however, points to the presence of simple adhered water molecules in the brown dimeric species and the presence of both

coordinated and lattice water molecules in β -picoline and o-phenanthroline varieties.

It appears that the primary ligand (ONSH₂) undergoes 'thione-thiol' tautomerism in aqueous alcoholic solution and the 'thiol' form [Ib] of the ligand participates in complexation as indicated above by i.r. data with formation of Cu-O, Cu-N and Cu-S bonding. A tacit support for such a proposition is brought out more clearly from a far i.r. study (recorded upto 200 cm⁻¹) of [Cu(ONS)]₂.2H₂O. The newly developed bands at 430 cm⁻¹(ms)/400 cm⁻¹(w), 340 cm⁻¹(bs) and 280 cm⁻¹(w) in the spectrum may be assigned to $\nu\text{Cu}-\text{O}^{27}$, $\nu\text{Cu}-\text{S}^{28}$ and $\nu\text{Cu}-\text{N}$ (pz. ring)²⁹ respectively. Thus the compound, 1-thiocarbonyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid (ONSH₂) functions as a diprotic ONS-tridentate in forming complexes with Cu(II) ion and the following structural scheme (Fig. 2) for the seemingly dimeric species (hydrated variety) with the formation of the mixed-ligand complexes seem reasonable.

Fig. 2

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